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Nanocomposites, their Characterization and Study of their Antimicrobial Property

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ABSTRACT

This research work aims to create nanocomposite materials by adding nanofiller, characterize them and then look into their antimicrobial qualities. Here PMMA (poly methyl methacrylate) polymer is taken as the matrix material and In order to create ZnO-PMMA nanocomposite polymers, ZnO nanopowder is added as the filler material. Then their structures are studied by using various instruments like FTIR, XRD and thermometric gravimetric properties are studied by TGA. Then the antimicrobial property of these nanocomposites is studied in this work to find the zone of inhibition of each nanocomposite. The PMMA-ZnO nanopolymers/nanocomposites were successfully prepared by insitu- polymerisation method. The interaction between PMMA and ZnO was evidenced by FTIR. The Xray diffraction patterns have been utilised to study the structure of PMMA/ZnO nanopolymers/nanocomposites. In thermogravimetric analysis it was found that the thermal stability of PMMA/ZnO nanopolymers/nanocomposites increased as compared to virgin PMMA. The improvement of the thermal stability of PMMA is due to the uniform distribution of ZnO. The antimicrobial property of nanocomposites is studied here.

Keywords: Polymerisation, ZnO nanopowder, Nanomaterial product

**Synthesis of ZnO-
PMMA**

INTRODUCTION

A nanocomposite is a multiphase solid material that has structures with nanoscale repeat intervals between the various phases that comprise it, or one phase that has one, two, or three dimensions less than 100 nanometers (nm). Although porous media, colloids, gels, and copolymers can all be included in this term in its broadest sense, it is more commonly understood to refer to the solid combination of a bulk matrix and one or more nano-dimensional phases that differ in their properties because of structural and chemical differences.

The mechanical, electrical, thermal, optical, electrochemical, catalytic properties of the nanocomposite will differ markedly from that of the component materials [13]. There have been suggested size limits for these effects: <5 nm for catalytic activity, <20 nm for softening a hard magnetic material, <50 nm for changes in refractive index, and <100 nm for superparamagnetic, mechanical strengthening, or limiting matrix dislocation displacement.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methods of Preparation of PMMA and PMMA-ZnO Nanocomposites

About 50 milliliters of water were first taken for this project, placed in a beaker, and then heated. Then the temperature of the water was measured with a thermometer and the temperature of the water was adjusted till the temperature becomes stand still between 60° C to 70° C. The heating mantle was used to heat the polymer solution for polymerization.

Then some 10 ml. MMA (Methyl methacrylate) monomer was taken in a separating funnel then some (nearly 10 ml.) H₃PO₄ (phosphoric acid) was added to the monomer then it was shaken for 15 minutes properly. So that the stabilizers attached to the monomers are washed away. Now out of two layers seen the

lower layer was poured down and separated from the upper layer. Now some (nearly 10 ml.) NaOH (Sodium hydroxide) was added to the monomer MMA then it was shaken for 15 minutes properly. So that the stabilizers attached to the monomer are washed away further. Then out of the two layers are formed here the lower layer is separated from the upper layer from the separating funnel. Then some distilled water (nearly 10 ml.) was added to the monomer kept in the separating funnel then it was shaken for 15 minutes properly. Then out of the two layers are formed here the lower layer is removed from the separating funnel. Now the monomer is free from stabilizers. Now 4 ml. MMA or monomer was taken with 14 ml. distilled water. Now the solution was sonicated for 20 minutes. After sonication 2 ml KPS (potassium peroxydisulphate) was added to the solution containing water and MMA as an initiator of polymerization. Now N₂ (nitrogen) gas was passed into the solution in a closed atmosphere to create inert atmosphere. Then the solution was stirred using magnetic stirrer for nearly 2 and ½ hours to 3 hours to allow the polymerization (i.e. PMMA formation) to take place. Now 2 ml ammonium iron sulphate hexahydrate was added to the solution to arrest or terminate the polymerization process. Then the solution was stirred for 10 minutes. The filtrate was washed with water twice. Then the solution was filtered by a filter paper overnight. Then the filtrate was dried in hot air oven at 65 ° C overnight. Then the dried filtrate which is the polymer was ground to powder form with mortar and pestle. Now the powdered PMMA polymer is analysis.

Now to prepare 1 % ZnO nanocomposite 4 ml washed polymer was taken to which 14 ml. distilled water was added and it was

sonicated for 20 minutes. Then 1 % ZnO (0.03768 gm. ZnO) was added to the solution. Now it was sonicated for 20 minutes. After sonication 2 ml KPS (potassium peroxodisulphate) was added to the solution containing water and MMA as an initiator of polymerization. Now N₂ (nitrogen) gas was passed into the solution in a closed atmosphere to create inert atmosphere [12].

Then the solution was stirred using magnetic stirrer for nearly 2 hours and ½ hours to 3 hours to allow the polymerization (i.e. PMMA- ZnO polymer formation) to take place. Now 2 ml ammonium iron sulphate hexahydrate was added to the solution to arrest or terminate the polymerization process. The solution was stirred for 10 minutes. Then the solution was filtered by a filter paper overnight. In between the filtrate was washed with water twice. Then the filtrate was dried in hot air oven at 65° C overnight. Then the dried filtrate which is the polymer was ground to powder form with mortar and pestle. Now the powdered 1 % ZnO nanocomposite polymer is ready for analysis.

Similarly 3% (0.11304 gm. ZnO) ZnO nanocomposite polymer, 5% (0.1884 gm. ZnO) ZnO nanocomposite polymer, 7% (0.26376 gm. ZnO) ZnO nanocomposite polymer, 8 % (0.30144 gm. ZnO) ZnO nanocomposite polymers were synthesized by following the above mentioned method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR Analysis of ZnO and ZnO-PMMA Nanocomposites

To see how PMMA and ZnO interacted, FTIR analyses of PMMA, ZnO-PMMA, and ZnO were performed. The FTIR spectra of the samples like PMMA, ZnO and PMMA + 3 % ZnO nanocomposite as obtained are given below in graphical forms in Figure 1 and the combined curves of both PMMA, ZnO and PMMA + 3 % ZnO nanocomposite are given in Figure 1. In the spectrum of nano-ZnO particle, the appearance of peak at 3410 cm⁻¹ in Figure 2 indicates the presence of -OH. The absorption peaks in the region 2800– 3000 cm⁻¹. Figure 1 correspond to the CH₂ and CH₃ group of PMAA. The strong absorption bands of 1550 cm⁻¹ and 1390 cm⁻¹ should belong to C=O of PMAA. Compared with the absorption bands of C=O of PMAA at 1575 and 1410 cm⁻¹, the shift of absorption band is possible due to the interaction between COO⁻ and ZnO to form poly(zinc methacrylate) complex on the surface of nano-ZnO. In addition, the characteristic peaks at 1150~1250cm⁻¹ are corresponding to the stretching vibrations of C–O–C in PMMA. It was concluded that the PMMA polymer chains were anchored on the ZnO nanoparticle surface. Therefore, these polymer chains can hinder the aggregation of ZnO nanoparticles.

Fig. 1: FTIR Spectra of PMMA, ZnO and PMMA + 3 % ZnO.

XRD Analysis of ZnO and ZnO-PMMA Nanocomposites

The XRD patterns of the samples like ZnO, PMMA and PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA + 10 % ZnO as obtained are given below in graphical forms [10,11]. To investigate the influence of PMAA on the crystalline structure of ZnO nanoparticles, the X-ray diffraction patterns of the particles before and after the modification were recorded in Figure 2. It is clear that except for a weak amorphous peak appearing at 2θ from 25 to 35, the spectra of composite particles are almost same as those of pure ZnO

nanoparticles, implying that the spectra of PMAA-modified ZnO nanoparticles are almost as same as those of the unmodified particles, implying that the modification has not altered the crystalline structure of the ZnO nanoparticles [8,9]. Nevertheless, the diffraction peaks of modified ZnO nanoparticles are fewer sharp than untreated ZnO nanoparticles, which illustrates that the presence of PMAA induces the decrease of the crystallite size. It implies that a little of Zn was probably consumed to form poly (zinc methacrylate) complex on the surface of nano-ZnO.

Fig. 2: XRD Spectra of PMMA, ZnO and PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA + 10 % ZnO.

TGA Analysis of ZnO and ZnO-PMMA Nanocomposites

The TGA analysis of ZnO, PMMA and PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA + 10 % ZnO nanocomposites were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere in the temperature range from 10° C to 800° C. The TGA curves of the pure PMMA and PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA + 10 % ZnO nanocomposites are shown in Figure 1 and 2. which contains all the curves together.

The PMMA nanocomposites (i.e. - PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA +

10 % ZnO nanocomposites) lost more weight and got more degraded than the pure PMMA decomposition. The pure PMMA decomposed completely at about 400 °C. However, PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA + 10 % ZnO nanocomposites got degraded some 40 °C latter i.e. nearly at 440 °C and the nanocomposites remained undecomposed by more than 1% to 40% at this temperature as shown in Figure 3. It could be concluded that the addition of the nanoparticles had improved the thermal properties of the nanocomposites obtained and the improvement depends on the amounts of nanoparticles added.

Fig. 3: TGA analysis of ZnO, PMMA and PMMA +1 % ZnO, PMMA + 3 % ZnO, PMMA + 5 % ZnO, PMMA + 7 % ZnO, PMMA + 10 % ZnO nanocomposites.

Study of the Anti-Microbial Properties of ZnO and ZnO-PMMA Nanocomposites

Method of study of anti-microbial property

The samples (PMMA/ZNO nanocomposites) were dissolved in Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) for anti-microbial bioassay. Anti-microbial

activities were determined by Agar Cup diffusion method against four bacterial pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*) and four pathogenic fungi (*Candida albicans*, *Candida krusei*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Candida Viswanathii*). The test pathogens were obtained from Institute of Microbial

Technology (IMTECH), Chandigarh, India. Nutrient Agar (NA) plates were inoculated with overnight culture of each bacterial suspension. Similarly, for the fungal pathogens, Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates were inoculated with each fungal suspension. The plates with the inoculated organisms were evenly spread out with sterile cotton swabs. Agar Cups were prepared by scooping out the media with a sterile cork borer (10mm diameter). The cups were then filled with 100µl of the PMMA/ZNO nanocomposites which were dissolved in DMSO to get a concentration of 1mg/ml. the plates were then incubated at 36±1°C for 24hours and

48 hours for bacterial and fungal pathogens respectively.

Result of the study of anti-microbial property

In the present research study of the antimicrobial property of nanocomposites, it was found that with increase in the concentration of ZnO the zones of inhibition of the nanocomposites increase, but the virgin PMMA does not have negligible zones of inhibition. ZnO gives a better zone of inhibition [3,6]. The zones of inhibition all the compounds are given in graphical form in Figure 4 below.

Fig. 4: Anti-microbial activity of PMMA/ZnO nanocomposite against test Pathogens
 Sa: *Staphylococcus aureus*, Bs: *Bacillus subtilis*, Pa: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*,
 Ec: *Escherichia coli*, Ca: *Candida albicans*, Ck: *Candida krusei*,
 Tm: *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and Cv: *Candida viswanathii*

Photos of anti-microbial activities taken showing the zone of inhibition are given below.

CONCLUSION

The PMMA-ZnO nanoparticles/nanocomposites were successfully prepared by insitu-polymerisation method. The interaction between PMMA and ZnO was evidenced by FTIR. The Xray diffraction patterns have been utilised to study the structure of PMMA/ZnO

nanopolymers/nanocomposites. In thermogravimetric analysis it was found that the thermal stability of PMMA/ZnO nanoparticles/nanocomposites was increased as compared to virgin PMMA [2,7]. The improvement of the thermal stability of PMMA is due to the uniform distribution of ZnO. In the present research the study of the antimicrobial property shows that with increase in the concentration of ZnO the zone of inhibition of the nano composites increases, but the virgin PMMA don't have or negligible zone of inhibition [4,5]. As a matter of further future study of this research work pellets can be made from the ZnO, PMMA and ZnO-PMMA nanocomposites and their electrical properties can be studied to know their conductance [1]. If polymers are prepared from ZnO-PMMA nanocomposites then they are biodegradable as the ZnO-PMMA nanocomposite polymers can be decomposed by microbes as per our antimicrobial property study.

REFERENCES

1. Kamigaito, O. (1991). What can be improved by nanometer composites? *Journal of the Japan Society of Powder and Powder Metallurgy*, 38(3), 315–321. In A. Kelly (Ed.), *Concise encyclopedia of composite materials* (1994 ed.). Elsevier Science.
<https://doi.org/10.2497/jjspm.38.315>
2. José-Yacamán, M., Rendón, L., Arenas, J., & Serra Puche, M. C. (1996). Maya blue paint: An ancient nanostructured material. *Science*, 273(5272), 223–225.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.273.5272.223>
3. Theng, B. K. G. (1979). *Formation and properties of clay-polymer complexes*. Elsevier.
4. Ajayan, P. M., Schadler, L. S., & Braun, P. V. (2003). *Nanocomposite science and technology*. Wiley.
5. Kruis, F. E., Fissan, H., & Peled, A. (1998). Synthesis of nanoparticles in the gas phase for electronic, optical and magnetic applications: A review. *Journal of Aerosol Science*, 29(5–6), 511–535.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-8502\(97\)10032-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-8502(97)10032-5)
6. Zhang, S., Sun, D., Fu, Y., & Du, H. (2003). Recent advances of superhard nanocomposite coatings: A review. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 167(2–3), 113–119.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972\(02\)00903-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972(02)00903-9)
7. Effenberg, G., Aldinger, F., & Rogl, P. (2001). *Ternary alloys: A comprehensive compendium of evaluated constitutional data and phase diagrams*. Materials Science International Services.
8. Birkholz, M., Albers, U., & Jung, T. (2004). Nanocomposite layers of ceramic oxides and metals prepared by reactive gas-flow sputtering. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 179(2–3), 279–285.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972\(03\)00865-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972(03)00865-X)
9. Lalwani, G., Henslee, A. M., Farshid, B., Parmar, P., Lin, L., Qin, Y. X., Kasper, F. K., Mikos, A. G., & Sitharaman, B. (2013). Tungsten disulfide nanotubes reinforced biodegradable polymers for bone tissue engineering. *Acta Biomaterialia*, 9(9), 8365–8373.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2013.05.018>

10. Gash, A. E. (n.d.). *Making nanostructured pyrotechnics in a beaker*.
11. Gash, A. E. (n.d.). *Energetic nanocomposites with sol-gel chemistry: Synthesis, safety, and characterization (LLNL UCRL-JC-146739)*.
12. Ryan, K. R., Gourley, J. R., & Jones, S. E. (2008). Environmental anomalies at the World Trade Center: Evidence for energetic materials. *The Environmentalist*, 29, 56. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-008-9182-4>
13. Manias, E. (2007). Nanocomposites: Stiffer by design. *Nature Materials*, 6(1), 9–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat1812>